

ADDITIVE BASES OF FINITE ABELIAN GROUPS OF RANK 2

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Abstract

Let G be a finite abelian group and p be the smallest prime dividing $|G|$. Let S be a sequence over G . We say that S is regular if for every proper subgroup $H \subsetneq G$, S contains at most $|H| - 1$ terms from H . Let $c_0(G)$ be the smallest integer t such that every regular sequence S over G of length $|S| \geq t$ forms an additive basis of G , i.e., $\langle S \rangle = G$. The invariant $c_0(G)$ was first studied by Olson and Peng in the 1980s, and since then it has been determined for all finite abelian groups except for the groups with rank 2 and a few groups of rank 3 or 4 with order less than 10^8 . In this paper, we focus on the remaining case concerning groups of rank 2. It was conjectured by Gao et al. (Acta Arith. 168 (2015) 247-267) that $c_0(G) = m(G)$. We confirm the conjecture for the case when $G = C_{n_1} \oplus C_{n_2}$ with $n_1 | n_2$, $n_1 \geq 2p$, $p \geq 3$ and $n_1 n_2 \geq 72p^6$.

1. Introduction and Main Results

Let G be a finite abelian group, written additively, p be the smallest prime dividing $|G|$ and $r(G)$ denote the rank of G . Let S be a sequence over G . We say that S is an *additive basis* of G if every element of G can be expressed as the sum over a nonempty subsequence of S .

Let $\text{cr}(G)$ denote the smallest integer t such that every subset of G of cardinality at least t is an additive basis of G . In 1964, Erdős and Heilbronn [1] proposed the problem of determining $\text{cr}(G)$, and it was completely determined by 2009 through many authors' efforts (see [2, 3] and their references).

For every subgroup H of G , let S_H denote the subsequence of S consisting of all terms of S contained in H . We say that S is a *regular sequence* over G if $|S_H| \leq |H| - 1$ holds for every proper subgroup $H \subsetneq G$. With this definition, we can generalize the above problem by considering regular sequences instead of subsets forming an additive basis. Actually, a similar generalization for sumsets can be found in [10, 11]. It is reasonable to study regular sequences, as it can be easily proved that if S is not a regular sequence, then there exists a proper regular subsequence T of S such that $\sum_0(S) = \sum_0(T)$ (see [8, Lemma 2.2]). Let $\text{c}_0(G)$ denote the smallest integer t such that every regular sequence over G of length at least t is an additive basis of G . The problem of determining $\text{c}_0(G)$ was first proposed by Olson and it was conjectured that $\text{c}_0(C_p \oplus C_p) = 2p - 1$. In 1987, Peng proved this conjecture and further determined $\text{c}_0(G)$ for all finite elementary abelian p -groups ([13, 14]). Those results and techniques used for determining $\text{c}_0(G)$ have been successfully applied to the study of nonunique factorization ([7]). Recently, the problem related to the additive basis of a finite abelian group has been investigated by several authors ([4, 8, 15, 16, 17]). Let

$$m(G) = \begin{cases} |G|, & \text{if } G \text{ is cyclic,} \\ 2p - 1, & \text{if } G = C_p \oplus C_p, \\ kp + 2p - 3, & \text{if } G = C_p \oplus C_{pk} \text{ and } k \geq 2, \\ \frac{|G|}{p} + p - 2, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It has been proved that $\text{c}_0(G) = m(G)$ for any of the following finite abelian groups:

- (1) G is cyclic ([4, Theorem 1.1(1)]);
- (2) $|G|$ is even ([4, Theorem 1.1(2)]);
- (3) $r(G) \geq 4$ and $G \neq C_3^3 \oplus C_{3n}$ where $n > 3$ is odd and is not a power of 3 with $|G| < 3.72 \times 10^7$ ([15, Theorem 1.2(1)] and [8, Theorem 1.2]);
- (4) $r(G) = 3$ and either $p \geq 11$ or $3 \leq p \leq 7$ with $|G| \geq 3.72 \times 10^7$ ([15, Theorem 1.2(2)] and [8, Theorem 1.2]);
- (5) $r(G) \geq 2$ and G is a p -group ([4, Theorem 1.1(5)] and [16, Theorem 1]);
- (6) $G = C_3 \oplus C_{3q}$, where q is a prime ([4, Theorem 1.1(2)], [16, Theorem 1] and [17, Theorem 1.1]).

Clearly, by their definitions, $\text{c}_0(G) \geq \text{cr}(G)$. Moreover, $\text{c}_0(G) = \text{cr}(G)$ for all finite abelian groups with $r(G) \geq 3$ whose $\text{c}_0(G)$ has been determined. However, $\text{c}_0(G)$

and $cr(G)$ differ significantly when $r(G) = 1$. For $r(G) = 2$, the exact value of $c_0(G)$ seems mysterious and has only been determined for all finite abelian p -groups and abelian groups of even order.

In this paper, we focus our investigation on the remaining case when G is of rank 2. It was conjectured in [4] that $c_0(G) = m(G)$. We confirm this conjecture for the case when $G = C_{n_1} \oplus C_{n_2}$ with $n_1|n_2$, $n_1 \geq 2p$, $p \geq 3$ and $n_1n_2 \geq 72p^6$.

Theorem 1. *Let $G = C_{n_1} \oplus C_{n_2}$ with $n_1|n_2$, and $p \geq 3$ be the smallest prime divisor of $|G|$. If $n_1 \geq 2p$ and $|G| \geq 72p^6$, then $c_0(G) = |G|/p + p - 2$.*

2. Notation and Preliminaries

Suppose that $G_0 \subseteq G$ is a subset of G and $\mathcal{F}(G_0)$ is the multiplicatively written, free abelian monoid with basis G_0 . The elements of $\mathcal{F}(G_0)$ are called *sequences* over G_0 . We denote multiplication in $\mathcal{F}(G_0)$ by the bold symbol \cdot rather than by juxtaposition, and use brackets for all exponentiation in $\mathcal{F}(G_0)$.

A sequence $S \in \mathcal{F}(G)$ will be written in the form $S = g_1 \cdot \dots \cdot g_\ell$, where $|S| = \ell$ is the *length* of S . For $g \in G$, let $v_g(S) = |\{i \in [1, \ell]: g_i = g\}|$ denote the *multiplicity* of g in S . We call $\text{supp}(S) = \{g \in G: v_g(S) > 0\}$ the *support* of S . Let $h(S) = \max\{v_g(S): g \in G\}$. A sequence $T \in \mathcal{F}(G)$ is called a *subsequence* of S and is denoted by $T \mid S$ if $v_g(T) \leq v_g(S)$ for all $g \in G$. Denote by $S \cdot T^{[-1]}$ the subsequence of S obtained by removing the terms of T from S .

If $S_1, S_2 \in \mathcal{F}(G)$, then $S_1 \cdot S_2 \in \mathcal{F}(G)$ denotes the sequence satisfying that $v_g(S_1 \cdot S_2) = v_g(S_1) + v_g(S_2)$ for all $g \in G$. For convenience we write

$$g^{[k]} = \underbrace{g \cdot \dots \cdot g}_k \in \mathcal{F}(G)$$

for $g \in G$ and k a nonnegative integer.

Let $\sigma(S) = \sum_{g \in G} v_g(S)g \in G$ be the sum of S . Define

$$\sum(S) = \{\sigma(T): 1 \neq T \mid S\},$$

where 1 is the empty sequence, and

$$\sum_0(S) = \sum(S) \cup \{0\} = \{\sigma(T): T \mid S\}.$$

We call a sequence S a *zero-sum* sequence if $\sigma(S) = 0$, and a *zero-sum free* sequence if $0 \notin \sum(S)$. We note that a subset of G can be regarded as a sequence, so all above-mentioned concepts and notations regarding a sequence of G are valid for a subset of G . We say that a subset $A \subset G \setminus \{0\}$ is *2-zero-sum free* if A contains no two distinct elements with sum zero.

Let $D(G)$ denote the Davenport constant of G , which is defined as the smallest integer t such that every sequence S over G of length $|S| \geq t$ contains a nonempty zero-sum subsequence. Note that $D(C_{n_1} \oplus C_{n_2}) = n_1 + n_2 - 1$, where $1 \leq n_1 | n_2$ ([9, Theorem 5.8.3]).

For each subset A of G , denote by $\langle A \rangle$ the subgroup generated by A . Let $\text{st}(A) = \{g \in G : g + A = A\}$. Then $\text{st}(A)$ is the maximal subgroup H of G such that $H + A = A$. The following is the well known Kneser's theorem and a proof of it can be found in [12].

Lemma 1 (Kneser, [12, Theorem 4.4]). *Let A_1, \dots, A_r be nonempty finite subsets of an abelian group G , and let $H = \text{st}(A_1 + \dots + A_r)$. Then,*

$$|A_1 + \dots + A_r| \geq |A_1 + H| + \dots + |A_r + H| - (r - 1)|H|.$$

Lemma 2 ([4, Lemma 2.2]). *The inequality $c_0(G) \geq m(G)$ holds for every finite abelian group G .*

Lemma 3 ([4, Lemma 2.3]). *Let G be a finite abelian group and p be the smallest prime divisor of $|G|$. Let S be a regular sequence over G of length $|S| \geq \max\{|G|/p + p - 2, D(G)\}$. Let T be a nonempty subsequence of S . If $\sum(S) \neq G$, then*

- (1) $\text{st}(\sum_0(T)) = \{0\}$;
- (2) $|\sum_0(T)| \geq |T| + 1$.

We remark that since $|S| \geq D(G)$, we have $0 \in \sum(S)$. Thus $\sum(S) = \sum_0(S)$, and the above lemma follows immediately from [4, Lemma 2.3].

For a finite abelian group G and a positive integer k , let $f(G, k) = \min\{|\sum(S)| : S \text{ is a subset of } G \text{ with } |S| = k \text{ and } 0 \notin \sum(S)\}$. If $0 \in \sum(S)$ for every $S \subseteq G$ of $|S| = k$, we set $f(G, k) = \infty$. Let $f(k) = \min\{f(G, k) : G \text{ is a finite abelian group}\}$.

Lemma 4 ([5, Theorem 1.1]). *The inequality $f(k) \geq \frac{k^2}{6}$ holds for every positive integer k .*

3. Proof of Theorem 1

We first prove a few technical results.

Lemma 5. *Let G be a finite abelian group and $A \subseteq G \setminus \{0\}$. If $|A| \geq 6p(p + 1) + 1$, then there is a zero-sum free subset $B \subseteq A$ such that $|\sum_0(B)| \geq p|B| + 2$ with $|B| \leq 6p + 1$, where p is a nonnegative integer.*

Proof. It is sufficient to prove that there is a zero-sum free subset $B \subseteq A$ such that $|\sum(B)| \geq p|B| + 1$ with $|B| \leq 6p + 1$. We first prove that for every $k \leq 6p + 1$ there is a zero-sum free subset $B \subseteq A$ such that either $|B| = k$ or $|B| < k$ and $|\sum(B)| \geq p|B| + 1$.

We proceed by induction on k . If $k = 1$, then the result holds trivially. Assume that the result is true for each k ($k < 6p + 1$). We next prove it is also true for $k + 1$. By the induction hypothesis, there is a zero-sum free subset $B_0 \subseteq A$ such that either $|B_0| = k$ or $|B_0| < k$ and $|\sum(B_0)| \geq p|B_0| + 1$. If $|\sum(B_0)| \geq p|B_0| + 1$, then let $B = B_0$. Hence $|B| < k + 1$ and $|\sum(B)| \geq p|B| + 1$, so we are done. Thus we may assume that $|B_0| = k$ and $|\sum(B_0)| \leq p|B_0|$. It follows that $|\sum(B_0)| = |\sum(B_0)| \leq pk \leq 6p^2 \leq |A| - (6p + 1) < |A| - |B_0| = |A \setminus B_0|$. Hence, there is an element $g \in A \setminus B_0$ such that $g \notin -\sum(B_0)$. So, $B_0 \cup \{g\}$ is a zero-sum free subset of A . Set $B = B_0 \cup \{g\}$, and then the result holds for $k + 1$.

Next, let $k = 6p + 1$. We have just proved that there is a zero-sum free subset B of A such that either $|B| = 6p + 1$ or $|\sum(B)| \geq p|B| + 1$ and $|B| < 6p + 1$. If the latter is true, then we are done. So, we may assume that $|B| = 6p + 1$. By Lemma 4, $|\sum(B)| \geq f(6p + 1) \geq (6p + 1)^2/6 \geq p(6p + 1) + 1$ and again we are done. \square

Lemma 6. *Let G be a finite abelian group and p be the smallest prime divisor of $|G|$. Let T be a sequence over $G \setminus \{0\}$ and $H = \langle \text{supp}(T) \rangle$. Then $|\sum_0(T)| \geq |T| + 1$ if one of the following holds*

- (1) $|T| \leq p - 1$;
- (2) $|T| \leq 2p - 1$ and $|H| \geq 2p$.

Proof. Let $T = g_1 \cdot \dots \cdot g_k$. Then,

$$\sum_0(T) = \{g_1, 0\} + \dots + \{g_k, 0\}.$$

Let $M = \text{st}(\{g_1, 0\} + \dots + \{g_k, 0\})$. If $M = \{0\}$, then by Lemma 1, $|\sum_0(T)| = |\{g_1, 0\} + \dots + \{g_k, 0\}| \geq k + 1 = |T| + 1$ as desired.

Next we assume $M \neq \{0\}$, so $|M| \geq p$.

(1) Since $k = |T| \leq p - 1$, we have $|\sum_0(T)| = |\{g_1, 0\} + \dots + \{g_k, 0\}| = |\{g_1, 0\} + \dots + \{g_k, 0\} + M| \geq |M| \geq p \geq k + 1 = |T| + 1$.

(2) If $M \supseteq H$, then as above $|\sum_0(T)| \geq |M| \geq |H|$. Since $|H| \geq 2p$ and $|T| \leq 2p - 1$, we have $|\sum_0(T)| \geq 2p \geq |T| + 1$. Next we assume that $\{0\} \neq M \not\supseteq H$. Clearly, $\sum_0(T) = \{g_1, 0\} + \dots + \{g_k, 0\} \subsetneq M$. Thus $g_i \notin M$ for some $1 \leq i \leq k$, and so $|\{g_i, 0\} + M| = 2|M|$. By Lemma 1, $|\sum_0(T)| = |\{g_1, 0\} + \dots + \{g_k, 0\}| \geq 2|M| \geq 2p \geq |T| + 1$ as desired. \square

As a consequence, we obtain the following corollary, which will be used in the proof of Lemma 7.

Corollary 1. *Let G be a finite abelian group and p be the smallest prime divisor of $|G|$. Let S and T be sequences over G . Suppose $g \notin \langle \text{supp}(S) \rangle$ for every $g \mid T$. Then $|\sum_0(T \cdot S)| \geq (|T| + 1)|\sum_0(S)|$ if one of the following holds*

- (1) $|T| \leq p - 1$;
- (2) $|T| \leq 2p - 1$ and $|\langle \text{supp}(T \cdot S) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(S) \rangle| \geq 2p$.

Proof. Let $\varphi : \langle \text{supp}(T \cdot S) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{supp}(T \cdot S) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(S) \rangle$ be the canonical epimorphism. Let $T = g_1 \cdot \dots \cdot g_k$ and $\varphi(T) = \varphi(g_1) \cdot \dots \cdot \varphi(g_k)$. Since $g_i \notin \langle \text{supp}(S) \rangle$ for every $i \in [1, k]$, we have $\varphi(g_i) \neq 0$ for $i \in [1, k]$. Thus $\varphi(T)$ is a sequence over $\varphi(G) \setminus \{\varphi(0)\}$. By Lemma 6, we have $|\sum_0(\varphi(T))| \geq |\varphi(T)| + 1 = |T| + 1$. Therefore, $|\sum_0(T \cdot S)| \geq |\sum_0(\varphi(T))| \cdot |\sum_0(S)| \geq (|T| + 1)|\sum_0(S)|$. \square

Lemma 7. *Let G be a finite abelian group and p be the smallest prime divisor of $|G|$. Let $R = R_1 \cdot R_2$ be a sequence over G . If R satisfies the following three conditions:*

- (1) $|R_1| \geq 2p - 1$;
- (2) $g \notin \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle$ for all $g \mid R_1$;
- (3) $|\langle \text{supp}(R) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle| \geq 2p$;

then there exists a subsequence $R'_1 \mid R_1$ such that $|R'_1| = 2p - 1$ and $|\sum_0(R'_1 \cdot R_2)| \geq 2p(|R'_2| + 1)$ for every subsequence $R'_2 \mid R_2$.

Proof. If $\langle \text{supp}(R) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle$ is a group of prime order, then by (1) let R'_1 be an arbitrary subsequence of R_1 with length $|R'_1| = 2p - 1$. By (2), $\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle$ is not trivial, and thus we must have $\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle = \langle \text{supp}(R) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle$. Therefore, by (3),

$$|\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle| = |\langle \text{supp}(R) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle| \geq 2p.$$

Next we assume that $|\langle \text{supp}(R) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle|$ is a composite number. Since $\langle \text{supp}(R_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle = \langle \text{supp}(R) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle$, by (1) and (2), there exists a subsequence $R'_1 \mid R_1$ with $|R'_1| = 2p - 1$ such that $|\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle|$ is a composite number. Since p is the smallest prime divisor of $|G|$, we have $|\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle| \geq p^2 \geq 2p$. So we can always choose a subsequence $R'_1 \mid R_1$ such that

$$|R'_1| = 2p - 1 \quad \text{and} \quad |\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle| \geq 2p.$$

Since $R'_2 \mid R_2$ is a subsequence of R_2 , we have $\langle \text{supp}(R'_2) \rangle \leq \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle$ and thus

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R'_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R'_2) \rangle| &= |\langle \text{supp}(R'_1), \text{supp}(R'_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R'_2) \rangle| \\ &\geq |\langle \text{supp}(R'_1), \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle| \\ &= |\langle \text{supp}(R'_1 \cdot R_2) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(R_2) \rangle| \\ &\geq 2p. \end{aligned}$$

Note that by (2), $g \notin \langle \text{supp}(R'_2) \rangle$ for every $g \mid R'_1$. By Corollary 1(2) and Lemma 3(2), we have $|\sum_0(R'_1 \cdot R'_2)| \geq (|R'_1| + 1)|\sum_0(R'_2)| \geq 2p(|R'_2| + 1)$. \square

Lemma 8 ([4, Lemma 3.1]). *If A is a 2-zero-sum free subset of three elements in an arbitrary abelian group, then either $|\sum_0(A)| \geq 7$ or A contains some element of order two.*

We now prove our main result.

Proof of Theorem 1. Let $n = |G|$. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove $c_0(G) \leq n/p + p - 2$. Let S be a regular sequence over G of length $|S| = n/p + p - 2$. We only need to show that $\sum(S) = G$. Since $2p \leq n_1|n_2$, we have $n/p + p - 2 \geq n_1 + n_2 - 1 = D(G)$. Hence $0 \in \sum(S)$ and thus $\sum(S) = \sum_0(S)$.

Assume to the contrary that $\sum_0(S) \neq G$, that is, $|\sum_0(S)| < n$. Thus, by Lemma 3(1), we have $\text{st}(\sum_0(S)) = \{0\}$.

Suppose that $h(S) \leq 2p - 2$. If $|\text{supp}(S)| \leq 6p(p+1)$, then $|S| \leq |\text{supp}(S)| \cdot h(S) \leq 12p(p^2 - 1)$. Since $|S| = \frac{n}{p} + p - 2 \geq \frac{72p^6}{p} + p - 2 \geq 72p^5 > 12p(p^2 - 1)$, we get a contradiction. Hence $|\text{supp}(S)| \geq 6p(p+1) + 1$. By Lemma 5, we may choose $A_1 \subseteq \text{supp}(S) \subseteq G$, such that $|A_1| \leq 6p + 1$ and $|\sum_0(A_1)| \geq p|A_1| + 2$. Let $t \geq 1$ be the maximal integer such that S has a factorization

$$S = A_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A_t \cdot T$$

with $A_i \subseteq G$, $|A_i| \leq 6p + 1$ and $|\sum_0(A_i)| \geq p|A_i| + 2$ for every $i \in [1, t]$.

Note that if $S' \mid S$ is a subsequence of S , then S' has a factorization of $S' = A'_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A'_t \cdot T'$, where $A'_i \mid A_i$ for $i \in [1, t]$ and $T' \mid T$. On the other hand, if $A'_i \mid A_i$ for $i \in [1, t]$ and $T' \mid T$, then $S' = A'_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A'_t \cdot T'$ is a subsequence of S . So, $\sum_0(S) = \{\sigma(S') : S' \mid S\} = \{\sigma(A'_1) + \dots + \sigma(A'_t) + \sigma(T') : A'_i \mid A_i \text{ for } i \in [1, t] \text{ and } T' \mid T\} = \{\sigma(A'_1) : A'_1 \mid A_1\} + \dots + \{\sigma(A'_t) : A'_t \mid A_t\} + \{\sigma(T') : T' \mid T\} = \sum_0(A_1) + \dots + \sum_0(A_t) + \sum_0(T)$. Since $\sum(S) = \sum_0(S)$, we have

$$\sum(S) = \sum_0(S) = \sum_0(A_1) + \dots + \sum_0(A_t) + \sum_0(T).$$

By the maximality of t and Lemma 5, we have $|\text{supp}(T)| \leq 6p(p+1)$. Thus $|T| \leq |\text{supp}(T)| \cdot h(S) \leq 12p(p^2 - 1)$. Since $|A_i| \leq 6p + 1$ for each $i \in [1, t]$, we

have $t \geq \frac{|S|-|T|}{6p+1}$. By Lemma 3(2), $|\sum_0(T)| \geq |T| + 1$. Since $\text{st}(\sum(S)) = \{0\}$, by Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\sum_0(S)| &= |\sum_0(A_1) + \dots + \sum_0(A_t) + \sum_0(T)| \\ &\geq (|\sum_0(A_1)| - 1) + \dots + (|\sum_0(A_t)| - 1) + |\sum_0(T)| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^t (p|A_i| + 1) + |T| + 1 \\ &= p(|S| - |T|) + t + |T| + 1 \\ &\geq (p + \frac{1}{6p+1})(|S| - |T|) + |T| + 1 \tag{3.1} \\ &\geq n + \frac{n}{p(6p+1)} + p^2 - 2p - (p - \frac{6p}{6p+1})|T| + 1 \text{ (as } |S| = \frac{n}{p} + p - 2) \\ &\geq n + \frac{n}{p(6p+1)} + p^2 - 2p - \frac{12p^2(6p-5)(p^2-1)}{6p+1} + 1 \\ &\quad \text{(as } |T| \leq 12p(p^2-1)) \\ &\geq n + \frac{n}{p(6p+1)} - \frac{12p^2 \cdot 6p \cdot p^2}{6p+1} \\ &\geq n \quad \text{(as } n \geq 72p^6), \end{aligned}$$

yielding a contradiction. Therefore, we must have $h(S) \geq 2p - 1$. We choose $g_1 \in \text{supp}(S)$ such that

$$|S_{\langle g_1 \rangle}| = \max\{|S_{\langle g \rangle}| : g \in \text{supp}(S) \text{ and } v_g(S) \geq 2p - 1\}.$$

Let $S_1 = S_{\langle g_1 \rangle}$ and λ be the maximal integer such that S has a factorization

$$S = (T_1 \cdot S_1) \cdot (T_2 \cdot S_2) \cdot \dots \cdot (T_\lambda \cdot S_\lambda) \cdot S'$$

with the following properties:

- (1) $|T_i| = 2p - 1$ for each $i \in [1, \lambda]$;
- (2) for each $i \in [1, \lambda]$, $v_{g_i}(S_i) \geq 2p - 1$ for some $g_i \in G$; moreover, S_i contains all terms from $S \cdot ((T_1 \cdot S_1) \cdot (T_2 \cdot S_2) \cdot \dots \cdot (T_{i-1} \cdot S_{i-1}))^{[-1]}$ contained in $\langle g_i \rangle$;
- (3) $|\sum_0(T_i \cdot S'_i)| \geq 2p(|S'_i| + 1)$ for all subsequences $S'_i \mid S_i$, where $i \in [1, \lambda]$.

Now we prove

$$\lambda \geq 1.$$

We first show that $\langle \text{supp}(S) \rangle = G$. For otherwise, if $H = \langle \text{supp}(S) \rangle < G$, then $|H| \leq \frac{n}{p}$ where p is the smallest prime divisor of $|G|$. Since S is regular, we

have $|H| - 1 \geq |S_H| = |S| = \frac{n}{p} + p - 2 \geq |H|$, yielding a contradiction. Thus $\langle \text{supp}(S) \rangle = G$. It follows that $\langle \text{supp}((S \cdot S_1^{[-1]}) \cdot S_1) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(S_1) \rangle = G / \langle \text{supp}(S_1) \rangle$. Since $\langle \text{supp}(S_1) \rangle$ is a cyclic group, we have $|\langle \text{supp}(S_1) \rangle| \leq n_2$ and thus

$$|\langle \text{supp}((S \cdot S_1^{[-1]}) \cdot S_1) \rangle / \langle \text{supp}(S_1) \rangle| = |G / \langle \text{supp}(S_1) \rangle| \geq n_1 \geq 2p.$$

Note that

$$|S \cdot S_1^{[-1]}| \geq \frac{n}{p} + p - 2 - \frac{n}{p^2} \geq 2p - 1.$$

By the assumption of S_1 , we have $g \notin \langle \text{supp}(S_1) \rangle$ for all $g \mid S \cdot S_1^{[-1]}$. By Lemma 7, there exists a subsequence $T_1 \mid S \cdot S_1^{[-1]}$ such that $|T_1| = 2p - 1$ and $|\sum_0(T_1 \cdot S'_1)| \geq 2p(|S'_1| + 1)$ for all subsequences $S'_1 \mid S_1$. So, T_1 together with S_1 satisfies all three properties. Thus, $\lambda \geq 1$.

Next we distinguish the remaining proof into the following two cases according to the value of $h(S')$.

Case 1. $h(S') \leq 2p - 2$.

Let $t \geq 0$ be the maximal integer such that S' has a factorization

$$S' = A_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A_t \cdot T$$

with $A_i \subseteq G$, $|A_i| \leq 6p + 1$ and $|\sum_0(A_i)| \geq p|A_i| + 2$. By the maximality of t and Lemma 5, we have $|\text{supp}(T)| \leq 6p(p + 1)$. Thus $|T| \leq |\text{supp}(T)| \cdot h(S') \leq 12p(p^2 - 1)$. Since $|T_i \cdot S_i| \geq 4p - 2$ for each $i \in [1, \lambda]$, we have $\lambda \leq \frac{|S| - |S'|}{4p - 2}$. Similarly, $t \geq \frac{|S'| - |T|}{6p + 1}$. By Lemma 3(2), $|\sum_0(T)| \geq |T| + 1$. Since $\text{st}(\sum_0(S)) = \{0\}$, by Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\sum_0(S)| &= \left| \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} \sum_0(T_i \cdot S_i) + \sum_{j=1}^t \sum_0(A_j) + \sum_0(T) \right| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} (|\sum_0(T_i \cdot S_i)| - 1) + \sum_{j=1}^t (|\sum_0(A_j)| - 1) + |\sum_0(T)| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} (2p|S_i| + 2p - 1) + \sum_{j=1}^t (p|A_j| + 1) + |T| + 1 \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} (2p|T_i \cdot S_i| - (2p - 1)^2) + p(|S'| - |T|) + t + |T| + 1 \\ &\geq 2p(|S| - |S'|) - (2p - 1)^2\lambda + (p + \frac{1}{6p + 1})(|S'| - |T|) + |T| + 1 \\ &\geq (p + 1/2)(|S| - |S'|) + (p + \frac{1}{6p + 1})(|S'| - |T|) + |T| + 1 \\ &\geq (p + \frac{1}{6p + 1})(|S| - |T|) + |T| + 1 \\ &\geq n \quad (\text{as } |T| \leq 12p(p^2 - 1)), \end{aligned}$$

yielding a contradiction. We note that the last inequality was obtained by using a similar calculation as in (3.1).

Case 2. $h(S') \geq 2p - 1$.

There exists $g_{\lambda+1} \in G$ such that $v_{g_{\lambda+1}}(S') = h(S') \geq 2p - 1$. Let $S_{\lambda+1} = S'_{\langle g_{\lambda+1} \rangle}$ and $U = S' \cdot S_{\lambda+1}^{[-1]}$. Then

$$S = (T_1 \cdot S_1) \cdot (T_2 \cdot S_2) \cdot \dots \cdot (T_\lambda \cdot S_\lambda) \cdot S_{\lambda+1} \cdot U.$$

We next distinguish the rest of the proof into the following two subcases.

Subcase 2.1. $|U| \leq 2p - 2$.

By the choice of S_1 , we have $|S_{\lambda+1}| \leq |S_1|$. Since $|T_i \cdot S_i| \geq 4p - 2$ for each $i \in [2, \lambda]$, we have $\lambda - 1 \leq \frac{|S| - |S_1 \cdot T_1| - |S_{\lambda+1}| - |U|}{4p - 2}$. By Lemma 3(2), $|\sum_0(S_{\lambda+1} \cdot U)| \geq |S_{\lambda+1} \cdot U| + 1$. Since $\text{st}(\sum_0(S)) = \{0\}$, by Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\sum_0(S)| &= |\sum_0(T_1 \cdot S_1) + \sum_{i=2}^\lambda \sum_0(T_i \cdot S_i) + \sum_0(S_{\lambda+1} \cdot U)| \\ &\geq (|\sum_0(T_1 \cdot S_1)| - 1) + \sum_{i=2}^\lambda (|\sum_0(T_i \cdot S_i)| - 1) + |\sum_0(S_{\lambda+1} \cdot U)| \\ &\geq (2p|S_1| + 2p - 1) + \sum_{i=2}^\lambda (2p|S_i| + 2p - 1) + |S_{\lambda+1} \cdot U| + 1 \\ &\geq (p + 1/2)|S_1| + \sum_{i=2}^\lambda (2p|T_i \cdot S_i| - (2p - 1)^2) + (p + 1/2)|S_{\lambda+1}| + 2p \\ &= (p + 1/2)(|S_1| + |S_{\lambda+1}|) + 2p(|S| - |T_1 \cdot S_1| - |S_{\lambda+1}| - |U|) \\ &\quad - (2p - 1)^2(\lambda - 1) + 2p \\ &\geq (p + 1/2)(|S_1| + |S_{\lambda+1}|) + (p + 1/2)(|S| - |T_1 \cdot S_1| - |S_{\lambda+1}| - |U|) \\ &\quad + 2p \\ &= (p + 1/2)(|S| - |T_1| - |U|) + 2p \\ &\geq (p + 1/2)(n/p + p - 2 - (4p - 3)) + 2p \\ &\geq n \quad (\text{as } n \geq 6p^3 - 3p^2 - p), \end{aligned}$$

yielding a contradiction.

Subcase 2.2. $|U| \geq 2p - 1$.

Let $H = \langle \text{supp}(U \cdot S_{\lambda+1}) \rangle$. By the choice of $S_{\lambda+1}$, we have $\langle \text{supp}(S_{\lambda+1}) \rangle = \langle g_{\lambda+1} \rangle$, and $g \notin \langle g_{\lambda+1} \rangle$ for all $g \mid U$. If $|H/\langle g_{\lambda+1} \rangle| \geq 2p$, then by Lemma 7, we can find a subsequence $T_{\lambda+1} \mid U$ such that $|T_{\lambda+1}| = 2p - 1$ and $|\sum_0(T_{\lambda+1} \cdot S'_{\lambda+1})| \geq 2p(|S'_{\lambda+1}| + 1)$ for all subsequence $S'_{\lambda+1} \mid S_{\lambda+1}$. Therefore, $S_{\lambda+1}$ and $T_{\lambda+1}$ satisfy

Properties (1) – (3), yielding a contradiction to the maximality of λ . Therefore, we must have $|H/\langle g_{\lambda+1} \rangle| \leq 2p - 1$. Since $\langle g_{\lambda+1} \rangle$ is a cyclic subgroup of G , we have $|G/\langle g_{\lambda+1} \rangle| \geq n_1 \geq 2p$. Thus $H \neq G$. Therefore,

$$|H| \leq n/p \quad \text{and} \quad |S'| \leq |S_H| \leq n/p - 1 \quad (\text{as } S'|S_H \text{ and } S \text{ is regular}).$$

Suppose that $\text{supp}(S_i) \not\subseteq H$ for some $i \in [1, \lambda]$. Then let $S'_i = S_i \cdot g_i^{[-(p-1)]}$. We have

$$S = \left(\prod_{1 \leq j \neq i \leq \lambda} (T_j \cdot S_j) \right) \cdot (T_i \cdot S'_i) \cdot (g_i^{[p-1]} \cdot S').$$

Let $U' \mid U$ with $|U'| = p-1$. By Corollary 1(1) and Lemma 3(2), $|\sum_0(U' \cdot g_{\lambda+1}^{[2p-1]})| \geq (|U'| + 1)|\sum_0(g_{\lambda+1}^{[2p-1]})| = 2p^2$. By Lemma 3(1), $\text{st}(\sum_0(S')) = \{0\}$. Note that

$$\sum_0(S') = \sum_0(S' \cdot (U' \cdot g_{\lambda+1}^{[2p-1]})^{[-1]}) + \sum_0(U' \cdot g_{\lambda+1}^{[2p-1]}).$$

By Lemma 1 and Lemma 3(2), $|\sum_0(S')| \geq |\sum_0(S' \cdot (U' \cdot g_{\lambda+1}^{[2p-1]})^{[-1]})| + |\sum_0(U' \cdot g_{\lambda+1}^{[2p-1]})| - 1 \geq |S' \cdot (U' \cdot g_{\lambda+1}^{[2p-1]})^{[-1]}| + 2p^2 = |S'| + 2p^2 - 3p + 2$. Therefore, by Corollary 1(1),

$$|\sum_0(g_i^{[p-1]} \cdot S')| \geq (|g_i^{[p-1]}| + 1)|\sum_0(S')| \geq p|\sum_0(S')| \geq p|S'| + 2p^3 - 3p^2 + 2p.$$

As in Subcase 2.1, we have $\lambda - 1 \leq \frac{|S| - |T_i \cdot S_i| - |S'|}{4p-2}$. Since $\text{st}(\sum_0(S)) = \{0\}$, by Lemma 1,

$$\begin{aligned} |\sum_0(S)| &= \left| \sum_{1 \leq j \neq i \leq \lambda} \sum_0(T_j \cdot S_j) + \sum_0(T_i \cdot S'_i) + \sum_0(g_i^{[p-1]} \cdot S') \right| \\ &\geq \sum_{1 \leq j \neq i \leq \lambda} (|\sum_0(T_j \cdot S_j)| - 1) + (|\sum_0(T_i \cdot S'_i)| - 1) \\ &\quad + |\sum_0(g_i^{[p-1]} \cdot S')| \\ &\geq \sum_{1 \leq j \neq i \leq \lambda} (2p|T_j \cdot S_j| - (2p - 1)^2) + (2p|S'_i| + 2p - 1) + p|S'| + 2p^3 \\ &\quad - 3p^2 + 2p \\ &= 2p(|S| - |S_i \cdot T_i| - |S'|) - (2p - 1)^2(\lambda - 1) + 2p(|S_i| - p + 1) + p|S'| \\ &\quad + 2p^3 - 3p^2 + 4p - 1 \\ &\geq (p + 1/2)(|S| - |S_i \cdot T_i| - |S'|) + 2p|S_i| + p|S'| + 2p^3 - 5p^2 + 6p - 1 \\ &= (p + 1/2)|S| + (p - 1/2)|S_i| - (p + 1/2)|T_i| - |S'|/2 + 2p^3 - 5p^2 + 6p \\ &\quad - 1 \\ &\geq (p + 1/2)(n/p + p - 2) - (2p - 1) - (n/p - 1)/2 + 2p^3 - 5p^2 + 6p - 1 \\ &\geq n, \end{aligned}$$

yielding a contradiction.

Next assume that $\text{supp}(S_i) \subseteq H$ for every $i \in [1, \lambda]$. Let

$$S'' = S_1 \cdot \dots \cdot S_\lambda \cdot S'.$$

Then $S'' \mid S_H$. Let

$$n' = |H| \leq n/p.$$

Since $S'' = S_1 \cdot \dots \cdot S_\lambda \cdot S'$ with $|S_i| \geq |T_i|$ for $i \in [1, \lambda]$, we have $|S''| \geq (|S| + |S'|)/2 \geq ((n/p + p - 2) + |U| + |S_{\lambda+1}|)/2 \geq (n' + |U| + |S_{\lambda+1}| + 1)/2$.

Let $T = h_1 \cdot h_2 \cdot S_{\lambda+1}$ where $h_1 \cdot h_2 \mid U$. Let $t \geq 0$ be the maximal integer such that S'' has a new factorization

$$S'' = A_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A_t \cdot W \cdot T$$

where each A_i is a 2-zero-sum free 3-subset of G , and W is a subsequence of S'' which contains no 2-zero-sum free 3-subset of G . Then

$$3t + |W| + |S_{\lambda+1}| + 2 = |S''| \geq (n' + |U| + |S_{\lambda+1}| + 1)/2 \tag{3.2}$$

and

$$\text{supp}(W) \subseteq \{u_1, -u_1, u_2, -u_2\}$$

for some distinct elements $u_1, u_2 \in H$. By Lemma 8, $|\sum_0(A_i)| \geq 7$ for $i \in [1, t]$.

We now show that $|W| > |U|$. Since $S'' \subseteq H$ and $|H| = n'$, we must have

$$\sum_0(S'') \subsetneq H, \quad \text{and thus} \quad |\sum_0(S'')| \leq n' - 1.$$

For otherwise, $\sum_0(S'') = H$ and thus $\text{st}(\sum_0(S'')) \supseteq H \neq \{0\}$. However, by Lemma 3(1), $\text{st}(\sum_0(S'')) = \{0\}$, yielding a contradiction. By Corollary 1(1) and Lemma 3(2), $|\sum_0(T)| \geq 3(|S_{\lambda+1}| + 1)$. It follows from Lemma 1 and 3(2) that

$$\begin{aligned} n' - 1 &\geq |\sum_0(S'')| = \left| \sum_{i=1}^t \sum_0(A_i) + \sum_0(W) + \sum_0(T) \right| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^t (|\sum_0(A_i)| - 1) + (|\sum_0(W)| - 1) + |\sum_0(T)| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^t 6 + |W| + 3(|S_{\lambda+1}| + 1) \\ &= 6t + |W| + 3|S_{\lambda+1}| + 3 \\ &= 2|S''| - |W| + |S_{\lambda+1}| - 1 \\ &\geq n' + |U| + 2|S_{\lambda+1}| - |W| \quad (\text{by (3.2)}). \end{aligned}$$

This gives

$$|W| \geq |U| + 2|S_{\lambda+1}| + 1 > |U|.$$

Note that $W \mid S'' \cdot S_{\lambda+1}^{[-1]} = S_1 \cdot \dots \cdot S_\lambda \cdot U$. In view of Property (2), if u_1 lies in $\text{supp}(S_j)$ for some $j \leq \lambda + 1$, then $v_{\pm u_1}(S'') = v_{\pm u_1}(S_j)$. Therefore, $u_1 \in \text{supp}(U)$ if and only if $v_{\pm u_1}(U) = v_{\pm u_1}(S'')$, meaning all terms equal to u_1 or $-u_1$ in S'' occur in U provided that $u_1 \in \text{supp}(U)$; and likewise for $-u_1, u_2$ and $-u_2$. Since $W \mid S''$ and $\text{supp}(W) \subseteq \{u_1, -u_1, u_2, -u_2\}$, we have $W \mid u_1^{v_{u_1}(S'')} \cdot (-u_1)^{v_{-u_1}(S'')} \cdot u_2^{v_{u_2}(S'')} \cdot (-u_2)^{v_{-u_2}(S'')}$. If $u_1 \cdot u_2 \mid W$ and $u_1 \cdot u_2 \mid U$, then by what we just proved, $u_1^{v_{u_1}(S'')} \cdot (-u_1)^{v_{-u_1}(S'')} \cdot u_2^{v_{u_2}(S'')} \cdot (-u_2)^{v_{-u_2}(S'')} \mid U$, so $W \mid U$, implying $|W| \leq |U|$, yielding a contradiction to $|W| > |U|$. Therefore, without loss of generality, we may assume that $u_1 \mid W$ and $u_1 \notin \text{supp}(U)$. Thus $u_1 \in \text{supp}(S_j)$ for some $j \leq \lambda + 1$. Since the sequence W is disjoint from $S_{\lambda+1}$ by construction, it follows that $u_1 \in \text{supp}(S_j)$ for some $j \leq \lambda$. In view of Property (2), we conclude that $-u_1 \in \text{supp}(S_j)$ and $v \notin \langle u_1 \rangle \leq \langle g_j \rangle$ for every $v \in \text{supp}(S_{\lambda+1})$. Write $W = W_1 \cdot W_2$ with

$$W_1 \mid u_1^{[v_{u_1}(S'')]} \cdot (-u_1)^{[v_{-u_1}(S'')]} \quad \text{and} \quad W_2 \mid u_2^{[v_{u_2}(S'')]} \cdot (-u_2)^{[v_{-u_2}(S'')]}.$$

Now fix $v \mid S_{\lambda+1}$. Let $V = W_1 \cdot v$ and $T' = T \cdot v^{[-1]}$. We obtain another factorization

$$S'' = A_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A_t \cdot V \cdot W_2 \cdot T'.$$

Since $v \notin \langle u_1 \rangle$, by Corollary 1(1) and Lemma 3(2), $|\sum_0(V)| \geq 2(|W_1| + 1)$. Note that

$$|S''| = 3t + |V| + |W_2| + |T'| - 1 = 3t + |W_1| + |W_2| + |S_{\lambda+1}| + 2. \tag{3.3}$$

As before, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} n' - 1 &\geq |\sum_0(S'')| = \left| \sum_{i=1}^t \sum_0(A_i) + \sum_0(V) + \sum_0(W_2) + \sum_0(T') \right| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^t (|\sum_0(A_i)| - 1) + (|\sum_0(V)| - 1) + (|\sum_0(W_2)| - 1) + |\sum_0(T')| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^t 6 + 2|W_1| + 1 + |W_2| + 3|S_{\lambda+1}| \\ &= 6t + 2|W_1| + |W_2| + 3|S_{\lambda+1}| + 1 \\ &= 2|S''| - |W_2| + |S_{\lambda+1}| - 3 \quad (\text{by (3.3)}) \\ &\geq n' + |U| + 2|S_{\lambda+1}| - |W_2| - 2 \quad (\text{by (3.2)}), \end{aligned}$$

implying

$$|W_2| \geq |U| + 2|S_{\lambda+1}| - 1 > |U|.$$

Next we consider W_2 . Since $\text{supp}(W_2) \subseteq \{u_2, -u_2\}$, if $u_2 \in \text{supp}(U)$, then as above, we obtain $W_2 \mid U$, implying $|W_2| \leq |U|$, giving a contradiction. Thus $u_2 \notin \text{supp}(U)$. As above, we conclude that $\{\pm u_2\} \subseteq \text{supp}(S_{j'})$ for some $j' \leq \lambda$ and $z \notin \langle u_2 \rangle \leq \langle g_{j'} \rangle$ for every $z \in \text{supp}(S_{\lambda+1})$. Since $|S_{\lambda+1}| \geq 2p - 1 \geq 5$, we can choose $z \mid S_{\lambda+1} \cdot v^{[-1]}$. Define $V = W_1 \cdot v$, $Z = W_2 \cdot z$ and $T'' = T \cdot v^{[-1]} \cdot z^{[-1]}$. Thus we obtain another factorization

$$S'' = A_1 \cdot \dots \cdot A_t \cdot V \cdot Z \cdot T''.$$

As before, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} n' - 1 &\geq |\sum_0(S'')| = |\sum_{i=1}^t \sum_0(A_i) + \sum_0(V) + \sum_0(Z) + \sum_0(T'')| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^t (|\sum_0(A_i)| - 1) + (|\sum_0(V)| - 1) + (|\sum_0(Z)| - 1) + |\sum_0(T'')| \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^t 6 + 2|W_1| + 1 + 2|W_2| + 1 + 3(|S_{\lambda+1}| - 1) \\ &= 6t + 2|W_1| + 2|W_2| + 3|S_{\lambda+1}| - 1 \\ &= 2|S''| + |S_{\lambda+1}| - 5 \quad (\text{by (3.3)}) \\ &\geq n' + |U| + 2|S_{\lambda+1}| - 4 \quad (\text{by (3.2)}) \\ &\geq n' \quad (\text{as } |U| \geq 2p - 1 \geq 5), \end{aligned}$$

yielding a contradiction. In all cases we have found contradictions. Thus we must have $\sum(S) = G$. This completes the proof. \square

We end this paper with the following remark.

Remark 1. It was proved that $f(6) = 19$ in [6, Theorem 1.2]. Thus Lemma 5 can be improved as follows: if $A \subseteq G \setminus \{0\}$ is a subset with $|A| \geq 21$, then there is a subset $B \subset A$ such that $|\sum_0(B)| \geq 3|B| + 2$ with $|B| \leq 6$. Therefore, when $p = 3$, we may relax the condition $|G| \geq 72p^6 = 52488$ to $|G| \geq 3045$, and the same proof as in Theorem 1 still works.

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